

Suggested Reading List on the Sustainability Paradox for the [US National Committee for CODATA](#)

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The following is my contribution to a reading list on the sustainability paradox, or the challenge of sustaining fiscal sustainability for data. Johnson & Bourne (2023) suggest that a system of data credit should be designed and enacted to give credit, specifically looking at the GBIF and biomedical data entities.

This reminds me of the reviewer credit schemes that journals were interested in pursuing to make reviewing for journals more enticing and allow those reviewers to receive a discount on their APCs or other services. This has come to fruition with <https://www.reviewercredits.com/> as an example. As one can see, most researchers would not be interested in what is offered as a reward.

With both examples, costs are still associated with administering and tracking credits. Then there's the education and buy-in to the credit schemes. And finally, this credit, which "can be exchanged for cash, data depositors, data downloads and data improvement services" (p. 6) would have to cross contracting lines and businesses, universities, libraries, research labs, etc. The administrative burden isn't accounted for as one cannot assume that a researcher can accept funds and then apply them without fiscal and legal oversight, often involving contracting offices.

Below are the sustainability articles I think are most helpful in detailing the different options to solve the sustainability challenge or those describing the costs associated with sustainability, with full citations available in the references.

1. OECD (OECD Science, 2017) detailed the different funding models available for research data repositories, listing several variables impacting the repository's business model.
2. The NSF-funded report "Making Research Data Publicly Accessible" (Hofelich Mohr, 2024), highlights estimates of what it costs per institution to support data management services. It is acknowledged that the full cost has not been gathered due to staff time and resources being required.
3. Invest in Open Infrastructure (Steinhart, 2024) released a report detailing the state of open infrastructure, including more than just the EU and US but Africa and Latin America. The impacts of AI, diamond open access, and digital sovereignty are considered.

4. Strecker et al. (2023) remind us that one business model is for a data repository to shut down, as seen in re3data. They found that repository shutdown was not rare: 6.2% of all repositories listed in re3data were shut down at least once a year since 2012. They found that the median age of a repository when shutting down was 12 years. This begs the question, what is long-term?
5. Humel et al. (2025) reminds us that sustainability is not just a biomedical or hard sciences data challenge. GLAM (galleries, libraries, archives, museums) and other cultural heritage entities face sustainability challenges.

Many other articles can pertain to sustainability, but the five above are the most pertinent to discussing data repository sustainability today (Abdin & De Pretis, 2024; Burns et al., 2013; Dillo & Hodson, 2015; Mishra et al., 2016; National Academies of Sciences et al., 2020; Schofield, 2010). There still isn't an answer, but the one constant is that all entities change and evolve and that the funding scheme can change throughout the entire infrastructure's lifespan.

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